

DESIGN AND TESTING OF AN AIRCRAFT COMPOSITE HINGE

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SUMMARY: A composite hinge has been designed to replace an existing metallic hinge on an aircraft aileron. The existing design consisted in a double webbed hinge which was then attached to the aileron by means of a fork fitting. The proposed single web hinge design aims at reducing the manufacturing cost. Two different composite material systems (thermoset and thermoplastic) were used to manufacture the single web hinges. The sizing of the hinge was performed by conducting a 3-D finite element analysis and using maximum allowable ply strain as the failure criteria. A special purpose test rig was employed to test all hinge specimens under the worst loading case. The initiation of failure in all hinges appeared to be delamination. The ultimate load expected during the operation of the hinge was met by the thermoplastic hinge. The initiation of failure on the thermoset hinge was just below the ultimate load.

KEYWORDS: composite hinge, testing and design, thermoplastics, RTM

INTRODUCTION

The metallic hinge of an aircraft aileron was used as the baseline design for a composite replacement part. A schematic drawing of the original design is shown in Fig. 1. The overall geometry of the new hinge was dictated by the aileron's front spar and also by the position of the fork fitting which connects the hinge to the wing. The composite hinge was designed as part of the Innovative Network Program from the Cooperative Research Centre for Advanced Composite Structures (CRC-ACS) and its principal objective was to reduce the manufacturing cost of the hinge while meeting the operational loads and conditions. Another main goal of the program was to compare the strength of thermoplastics vs thermoset composite materials when used in a highly loaded environment and validate the design cycle by testing the final components. The thermoset hinges were manufactured using liquid moulding technology (RTM) and non-crimp fabrics. The thermoplastic hinges were produced from carbon fiber fabric reinforced polyetherimide (CF/PEI) using compression moulding and co-consolidation procedures.

Four RTM hinges and five thermoplastic hinges were tested to failure. The initiation of failure in all hinges appeared to be delamination. The load at which delamination could be heard was lower for the RTM specimens. Once delamination was visible to the naked eye, fibre breakage occurred close to the web/flange intersection resulting in catastrophic failure. The thermoplastic hinges delaminated at a higher load and catastrophic failure was not observed

up to a tested load of 25 kN. No visible failure could be seen in the thermoplastic hinges while the extent of failure on the RTM hinges was very large once the load was removed. The ultimate load expected during the operation of the hinge was met by the thermoplastic hinge. The initiation of failure on the thermoset hinge was just below the ultimate load.

COMPOSITE HINGE DESIGN

Geometry

The overall geometry of the hinge was given by the front spar profile. The attachment method was to be chosen between mechanically fastening (original design), secondary bonding or a combination of the above methods. The positioning of the load pick-up point was also a fixed parameter. The above constraints left the following parameters as variables: number of webs, lay-up, flange and web thicknesses and number of parts in the hinge assembly.

To aid in deciding the more promising geometries, the actual aluminium hinge (Fig. 1, left) was analysed with finite element analysis so as to acquire an idea on load paths within the hinge. After comparing a number of concepts in terms of manufacturing cost it was decided to further develop the single web hinge concept (Fig. 1, right) which would reduce the number of parts on the hinge assembly from two to one. This would result in reduced manufacturing cost and weight.

Fig. 1: Actual aluminium hinge schematic (left) and proposed composite hinge (right)

Loads

The load cases applied to the aileron were obtained from the aircraft manufacturer and were divided into four main cases as follows:

Rib Line Loads

Upper Surface Suction

Distributed Surface Pressures

Induced Bending-Deflected

These cases were combined to give worst loading conditions on the aileron. The critical case which was chosen for the hinge analysis was the combination of cases (3) + (4). The combination of the above load cases was then resolved into aileron hinge reactions by adding the reaction of the individual load cases. The largest of these reactions (10000 N) was employed for all finite element analysis performed on the hinge. This value includes a 1.5 ultimate factor. Single hinge failure conditions could not be investigated due to lack of data from the aircraft manufacturer. The additional data required to do such analysis would include new induced bending parameters for each of the assumed failed hinges.

Finite Element Analysis

The lay-up for the hinge was chosen to be quasi-isotropic as the efficiency of highly orthotropic laminates around bolt/pin loaded holes is known to be inadequate. Furthermore, Hart-Smith [1] showed that the farther a laminate pattern is outside a quasi-isotropic lay-up, the more likely it is to fail prematurely by through-the-thickness cracks parallel to the maximum concentration of fibres.

The thickness of the web was calculated using finite element analysis under the following assumptions:

Plane stress conditions on the web

Failure criteria employed to size the web was of maximum allowable ply strain

Material properties were taken from prepreg properties as RTM properties were not available for the chosen material

The resulting web thickness was 12 mm and the chosen material was non-crimp fabric (ie 28 plies of non-crimp fabric resulting in an assumed cured ply thickness of 0.43 mm). The lay-up consisted in 14 plies of ± 45 and 14 plies of 0/90's as follows (0/90/45/-45/0/90/-45/45/0/90/-45/45/0/90/-45/45/0/90/45/-45/45/-45/0/90/45/-45/0/90)_s. The five outer plies at either side of the web continued onto the flange while 18 plies were dropped-off at the web/flange intersection. Finally, the flange section had two wrap-around plies resulting in an average flange thickness of 3.0 mm.

A more complete 3D FEA was then carried out using plate shell elements with laminate properties to assess the fastening method to be employed and to verify maximum ply strains at critical regions. It was observed during this analysis that secondary bonding of the hinge would introduce large peel stresses on the adhesive due to the rotation of the hinge with respect to the front spar of the aileron. As the most critical stress in adhesive materials is the peel stress and since the hinge is a primary structure, it was decided to mechanically fasten the hinge to the front spar.

The critical region was identified as being the web/flange intersection at the tensile side of the hinge. A shaded deformed plot of the hinge indicating the highly strained area (darkest = highly strained) is shown on Fig. 2.

Fig. 2: Deformed FEA plot showing highly strained region (darkest area)

Manufacturing aspects

The thermoset hinges were manufactured using liquid moulding technology with carbon biaxial non-crimp fabrics (COTECH C-BX 440) and RTM6 resin. A summary of the manufacturing procedure for the RTM hinge is outlined below:

Firstly, the material was kitted and tackified with powdered 'B-staged' RTM6 resin. The plies were then assembled in order and heat set over wooden forming blocks under vacuum in an oven at 100⁰ C for 30 minutes. After trimming the plies and closing the steel moulds, the tool was subjected to full vacuum and the resin injected at 200 kPa. Prior to this, the resin and tool were preheated to 80⁰ C and 120⁰ C respectively.

The thermoplastic composite hinges were produced from solvent impregnated fibre fabric reinforced polyetherimide (Ultem 1000) prepreg supplied by Ten Cate Advanced Composites, the Netherlands. The carbon fabric has a 5H satin woven construction. The prepreg has a resin content of 44.1 wt.%. PEI is an amorphous polymer and has a glass transition temperature of 217 °C [2]. Because of the complex geometry of the hinge, co-consolidation (in a hot press) technique was used to manufacture the hinge, in which several components with simple geometry were first produced by compression moulding technique and then were co-consolidated in a specially designed forming mould [3]. To get fully consolidated thermoplastic composite parts with high quality, the optimum forming conditions for this material, eg. forming temperature, holding time and forming pressure, were determined by an impregnation model developed by Hou et al [4]. The final void content in the thermoplastic composite hinge was less than 0.2%.

Both thermoset and thermoplastic hinges were finally trimmed to their final dimension and the holes for the fastening bolts were hand drilled. The main bush hole (load pick-up point) was drilled with a hole saw. The bush was then bonded with BR95 paste adhesive and left to cure at room temperature for over 24 hours.

Test Set-up and Results

A special purpose test rig was designed to test the hinge specimens under the worst loading case expected during operating conditions. The tests were carried out in an INSTRON 1195 machine under displacement control at 0.2 mm/min. A load-displacement curve was obtained from the data acquisition system and the test was filmed with a SVHS video camera so as to be able to determine crack initiation/propagation. The test set-up consisted of a hollow steel beam with two machined steel plates matching the profile of the front spar. These parts were bolted together to a larger steel plate fitted to the INSTRON testing machine. A schematic of the test set-up and an actual photograph of the loaded hinge specimen is shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3: Composite hinge test set-up

This load case was obtained from a full aileron model used during the INP. Four RTM hinges and five thermoplastic hinges were tested to failure. A typical load-displacement curve for both thermoplastics and thermoset composite hinges is shown in Fig. 4.

Both hinges behaved linearly up to the onset of the first crack growth in the tensile section, ie. in the bottom section the hinge being tested. After this event, non-linear behaviour was observed in both specimens. The main failure mode observed in all hinges appeared to be delamination in the tensile section (as shown in Fig. 5), while no failure indication was observed in the compression side. The load at which delamination started was much lower for the RTM specimens (from 9 up to 13.5 kN). Once delamination was visible to the naked eye, fibre breakage occurred close to the web/flange intersection resulting in catastrophic failure.

Fig. 4: Test results for highly loaded hinges made of (a) thermoplastic and (b) thermoset composite materials

Fig.5: Delamination at tensile section of hinge being tested

The thermoplastic hinges delaminated at a higher load level (above 15 kN) and catastrophic failure was not observed up to the specified maximum test load of 25 kN. After the load was removed, only small delaminations could be seen in the thermoplastic hinges while the extent of failure on the RTM hinges was substantial. A schematic diagram of the failure mechanisms

observed during test is shown in Fig. 6. The primary cause for delamination is due to excessive stress in the transverse direction within the matrix of a composite material. These large stresses in the tensile section of the hinge are mainly due to the out-of-plane deformation of the web/flange intersection resulting in the plies tending to pull away from the center line of the web. The failure mode observed in all hinges can aid in explaining the largest strength of the thermoplastic hinge when compared to the RTM version. Because delamination is dominated mainly by the matrix property [5], it is not surprising to see that the composite hinge made from a more toughened matrix composite system (thermoplastic) could survive a higher load than that made from a brittle matrix composite system (thermoset). The ultimate load expected during the operation of the hinge was met by the thermoplastic hinge. The initiation of failure on the thermoset hinge was just below the ultimate design load.

Fig. 6: Schematic diagram of failure mechanisms in tensile section of hinge

The effect of flange thickness distribution on the hinge strength was studied using thermoplastic composite hinges. The flange is made up of 10 layers of CF fabric/PEI prepregs and has a total thickness of 3 mm. To obtain continuous fibre orientation in the outer side of the hinge flange as well as in the web/flange intersection, these 10 layers of prepreg were divided into two groups, namely group a and group b (as indicated in Fig. 7). Group a corresponds to the build up around the web/flange intersection while group b forms the outer side of the flange. Two kinds of thermoplastic hinges with the same fibre orientation but with two different flange thickness distributions of $a/b = 7/3$ and $a/b = 5/5$ were tested. The results are shown in Fig. 7. As expected, hinge with $a/b = 7/3$ flange thickness distribution delaminated at a higher load level (17.8 kN) than that of $a/b = 5/5$ (15.5 kN). The reason is believed to be due to the fact that with more continuous fibre oriented in the load direction, the secondary tensile stresses within the matrix can be effectively reduced in the web/flange intersection.

Fig. 7: Effect of flange thickness distribution on thermoplastic composite hinge strength

CONCLUSIONS

The manufacturing cost could significantly be reduced by adopting the single web hinge concept. The overall reduction in cost would depend on recurrent manufacturing cost and expected number of hinges to be produced. The largest cost in the development of the single web hinge concept was the RTM tooling for the thermoset components and the co-consolidation moulds required for the thermoplastic hinges. The strength comparison between thermoplastic and thermoset hinge coupons showed; as expected; that due to the failure mode being delamination, the thermoplastic hinges performed significantly better. Furthermore, if a hot-wet load enhancement factor was to be considered, the thermoplastic hinges would present a larger advantage due to the fact that their mechanical properties do not degrade as much as those of thermoset materials. A fatigue test program for the thermoplastic hinges is being considered at the moment.

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